

Deliverable D20.2

Training Package for Digital Objects & Workflows

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1. Executive Summary

This first EOSC-ENTRUST Digital Objects and Workflows Training Package is primarily a documentation website[1] for the Five Safes TES federated workflow tools. The website covers broad concept definitions within the federated research space to provide context and develop understanding for interested parties, detailed exploration of categories of analyses when federating in TREs, and focused deployment and usage documentation for the Five Safes TES tools (which form the primary implementation of the work package deliverable D20.1[2]).

The training package website refers to additional material – much of which has been developed and published as part of this deliverable – in order to structure it appropriately and tailor the package to its target audience: **TRE Operators**, who will be installing and configuring the tools, using the deployed applications to manage the process, and therefore needing to understand how it will be used to run analysis. The package does however also recognise that TRE Operators cover a number of different responsibilities (such as Installers, Administrators, and Output Controllers), and the material does also cater to some additional audiences – Federation Operators and Researchers. This is detailed further below under the [Key Audiences](#).

This deliverable represents a snapshot of the referenced content at the time of delivery, for this first Training Package. The referenced materials will continue to be developed and evolve as we move towards the second Training Package (D21.2) and, it is expected, beyond.

The deliverable itself is comprised of several parts: this document, to give context to it as a deliverable piece as well as detail its production and summarise its content; the complete website source code and content[3], as referred to by a specific version controlled identifier; and reference to the live published version of the website[1], and the “Analysis Types for TREs” online resource[4] (which may continue to change over time).

The goal of this deliverable is to allow interested parties of the target audiences detailed within to learn what may be required to perform federated analyses of different types, as well as how that can practically be demonstrated today with the documented tooling (per D20.1). This will allow further widespread feedback on the approaches taken, the current tooling, and the documentation itself.

Users can start at the website directly, but may prefer to start with this document, providing the initial context and signposting by role or area of interest particular sections of the main training material.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	No
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	No
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	No
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18, WP19/20/21)	Yes
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	No
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for	No

<p>through a European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.</p>	<p>validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).</p> <p>4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15, WP19/20/21)</p> <p>5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).</p>	<p>No</p> <p>No</p>
<p>Objective 3 National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes</p>	<p>1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).</p> <p>2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).</p> <p>3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>No</p> <p>No</p> <p>No</p>
<p>Objective 4 The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (EOSC-ENTRUST) is embedded in the European</p>	<p>1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p> <p>2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>No</p> <p>No</p>

¹ Elizabeth Green et al. The present and future of the {Five Safes} framework. Nov. 2023, doi: 10.29012/jpc.831

Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.	3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)	No

3. Methods

The content of this deliverable has been developed as an online resource that collates and clarifies relevant material – on the concepts in federated analysis; standards used by the solution; and the installation, configuration and usage of the tools – into a tailored package for its target audience. Much of the training material started as records of internal guidance for the tooling development teams to aid with onboarding and collaboration. From here, the material was enriched following feedback as it spread beyond the internal development team to the work package at large, and also interested parties beyond the project willing to engage in understanding, deployment, and usage of the tooling, as part of an HDR UK collaboration with National Research Foundation Singapore[25]: Health Data Research UK[27], University of Swansea Medical School[28], .

This training package has incorporated that content, as well as reliable existing material, into an appropriate structure based mainly on areas and levels of interest to the primary audience, as detailed below.

The training package strives to reference existing material instead of repeating information already available – in particular the **Federated Research** documentation[5]. This includes the **Five Safes TES** Tools usage and deployment documentation, and the “**Analysis Types for TREs**” resource, both of which have been developed within this work package. The training package summarises and adds context to the relevant material, and presents it in a way targeted at the primary audience: **TRE Operators**. This keeps the package itself streamlined, and ensures referenced material remains up to date as the documentation develops further.

3.1. Delivery Scope

The scope of the deliverable per the D20.2 definition is to “provide an online resource explaining how to deploy workflows via the new TRE tooling” (**Five Safes TES**, per D20.1).

In discussion with the Training work package it was determined that a focus on material for TRE Operators was desirable.

With that in mind, the deliverable aims to cover certain key topics for key identified audiences.

3.1.1. Key Audiences

While the identified target audience is **TRE Operators**, it is not quite that simple when considering the broader context, the training material, and the differing responsibilities within TRE Administration.

As such, we've identified three key audiences, while also clarifying the distinct relevance of the material to different responsibilities of TRE Operators, and describing how the non-TRE Operator roles are still of interest in the context of this deliverable.

The audiences identified and considered in scope for this first training package are:

- **Federation Operators**, people responsible for coordinating a Federation of TREs
 - For the purposes of this training package, this includes managing the configuration of Projects and their TRE and User memberships in a Federation-centralised Submission Service
 - This role may be performed by a TRE Operator, e.g. within the “Front Door” TRE of a Federation, and as such is within the scope of this training package for TRE Operators.
- **TRE Operators**, people responsible for managing and operating a TRE. They are expected to have the appropriate technical knowledge and experience within their role. The material covers different aspects of TRE Operation that may be handled by different roles:
 - **Installers**, responsible for deploying and configuring the technical infrastructure and tools
 - **Administrators**, responsible for managing projects within the TRE
 - In the context of this training package, and in Five Safes TES, TRE Administrators will interact with the deployed tooling
 - **Output Controllers**, responsible for approving or rejecting project outputs for egress from the TRE.
- **Researchers**, people who want to submit analyses to TREs within a Federation in which they are an approved member of a Project, using this tooling.
 - This training package does not focus on this audience, however some Researcher activities are described within the material to provide TRE Operators with context and understanding of the process from a Researcher's perspective:
 - How to submit and run analyses
 - How to retrieve approved outputs

3.1.2. Key Topics

The training material aims to help TRE Operators achieve the following learning goals:

- Understand the concepts and standards used for Federated Workflow Processing
- Understand the components involved in the Five Safes TES Tools and their architectural and infrastructure requirements
- Know how to deploy and configure the Five Safes TES Tools, and understand how they may interact with existing components and processes within the TRE
- Understand how to run analyses via workflows using the tooling described
- Understand what analyses could be performed in a TRE within a federated context, subject to:
 - What the TRE finds acceptable
 - The capabilities of the tools in use (such as, but not limited to, the Five Safes TES tooling)

The sources of referenced material within the training package may contain material beyond the scope of these audiences and topics, increasing as they continue to grow, but the training package website serves to keep the scope focused.

3.2. Structure

This D20.2 document provides an overview of the training package, including context and details of its production.

The training package website has the following sections:

- An overview of the package, including its status as a deliverable, the goals of the Work Package 20, and information about the EOSC-ENTRUST Project.
- A description of the intended **audience**, giving similar context as this document for who the package is for, and why some material for other audiences is still relevant to the target **TRE Operator** role.
- A section providing general context on **Concepts and Standards** within the federated workflow processing space.
- A section discussing categorisation of analyses and how they relate to federated research in TREs. This incorporates the separate **Analysis Types for TREs** resource developed as part of this deliverable.
- A section on the **Five Safes TES** Tools, which provides structured targeted guidance for TRE Operators from the material in the Five Safes TES documentation that was developed within this work package. Subsections focus on:
 - An overview of the tools
 - Deployment of the components
 - User guides for Project setup within a Federation and its TREs

- User guides for processing workflows using the tools to run federated analysis.

3.3. Interaction with other work packages

As noted above, the training material was initially developed for internal clarity and reference, and then expanded to include guidance and context for collaborators and users. As a result, preparation of the material did not include specific interactions with the other work packages within the EOSC-ENTRUST project, though feedback was gathered from within the work package and also with other parties (beyond EOSC-ENTRUST) to determine the training materials' fitness for purpose in enabling deployment and usage of the demonstrator tooling.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1. Overview

The work for this deliverable has included preparing and structuring this document and the targeted work package, as well as developing material around both Five Safes TES and federated analyses.

The deliverable has been produced as a number of online resources, in addition to this document, as described in the Methods above.

The work accomplished in producing the deliverable can be summarised, with the resulting artifacts, as:

- **Main document (D20.2):** providing context for the deliverable and detailing its production.
- **Development of Deployment and Usage documentation for Five Safes TES**
- **Development of Analysis training material[4]**
- **Development of the primary training package website[1]** targeted at TRE Operators

The following sections provide further details on the work in each area.

4.2. Five Safes TES Documentation

Within this deliverable, we have developed key elements (as enumerated below) of the **Five Safes TES** documentation, around deployment and usage of the tools.

The resulting resource describes the components that make up the **Five Safes TES** tools and specifically:

- How to deploy them
 - Submission Requirements[6]
 - Submission Deployment[7]
 - TRE Components Requirements[8]
 - TRE Components Deployment[9]
 - Funnel Deployment[10]
 - Egress Configuration Guide[11]
- How to set up Projects in a Federation, including participating Researchers and TREs
 - Project Setup Overview[12]
 - Complete Project Setup Process[13]
 - Create a User[14]
 - Researcher Enrolment Guide[15]
 - Add a Person to a Federation[16]
 - Add a Person to a Project[17]
- How to configure the TRE tools to connect in a participating Federation[18]
- How TREs retain control of approval of Project participation[19]
- How analysis submitted to the Federation is federated to participating TREs, and TREs control egress of outputs
 - Submission API Token Guide[20]
 - Hello World Submission[21]
 - Demonstration Analysis Submission[22]

4.3. Analysis Types for TREs

The feasibility of different federated analytics depends on both the technical possibility, and the operational acceptability of different stages of analysis. The acceptability of an analysis can be divided into the acceptability of the output of the federated analysis, and the acceptability of the algorithm used to compute it.

For example, reporting the mean of some value for a population might be acceptable to all partners in the federation. Conceptually, the simplest way to calculate this mean would be to send the record-level data to one place, then calculate the value. However, this algorithm for computing the mean is likely to be an unacceptable disclosure risk for TREs.

An alternative algorithm to compute the mean would be for each TRE to calculate their local count of the population, and their local sum of the value. These summary statistics are sufficient for a central aggregator to calculate the overall mean, and the algorithm is then more acceptable to TREs. Within our categorisation of federated analyses, different

analyses are described using their output, reporting the StatBarn [23] the statistic comes under, and the data type of the output. Some analyses might not be computable in a way that satisfies TRE technical and operational requirements.

For example, federating the calculation of quantiles (e.g. percentiles or the median) is significantly more complicated than calculating the mean, so the common use-case of calculating the median may not be possible for some federations. There are statistics that federate well, such as the t-digest [24] that provide a very close approximation of quantiles, however. This categorisation records this relationship of one analysis providing an approximation of another, while keeping these separate so users are aware the analysis is not equivalent.

Each analysis then has one or more recorded algorithms, which defines which analysis is possible to compute, not just to publish. Each algorithm is categorised by its operational and technical requirements. The primary description of an analysis, which defines many of the other parameters, is whether an algorithm is decomposable; that is whether the computation can be split so that each TRE processes only its local data, producing summary statistics that an aggregator combines to produce the final result. In the example of the mean given above, the first approach where all the data are shared is not a decomposable algorithm, but the approach where the local count and sum are shared is fully decomposable.

The third category of decomposable is iteratively decomposable. For some algorithms, a single step of aggregation is insufficient. For example, if a federation wished to perform analysis of variance (ANOVA) with some post hoc tests, the ANOVA could be performed in one round of federation, then the post hoc tests carried out in a following round. Part of the reason for separating this kind of analysis from the other cases is that subsequent rounds will reveal some information about a TRE's dataset. A clearer example of disclosure risk in iterative algorithms is federated learning. The sharing of model updates with other nodes in a federation might present an unacceptable disclosure risk [29]. For this reason, for each algorithm, the observable data are reported, both what data can be observed, and by whom: the central aggregator, and the other TREs. This may be relevant for some federations in which the aggregator is trusted with information that the other TREs are not. A decomposable algorithm that only shares local information with an aggregator has different trust implications to one that shares information with other TREs through iteration.

These differences are mostly operational and depend on what TREs will accept, but also have technical implications, which are recorded. Other technical requirements of the algorithm are also reported, such as whether the execution of the algorithm requires the environment to be able to run complex, branching workflows, or can be executed in a more linear fashion. This allows the categorisation to distinguish between algorithms that

can be carried out using a paradigm like the task execution service (TES), or needs a technology like the workflow execution service (WES).

The possibility of using encryption techniques also determines what algorithms are possible for a federation. For example, the use of secure multiparty computation (MPC) allows the computation of otherwise non-decomposable analyses, including many survival analyses, without sharing individual data points. Other information about each algorithm can also be reported, such as the initial parameters that need to be shared across the network (for example an initial model for federated learning), academic references, and links to reference implementations.

Part of the analysis training material is a description of several common analyses using this framework, and a user interface to these descriptions, which allows users to filter analyses and algorithms by their TRE capabilities, making the material more easily accessible. Work is ongoing to provide different views of analyses in this framework, presenting the information to researchers and TREs in ways that will facilitate useful conversations about feasibility. This work will be valuable to the Drivers in EOSC-ENTRUST, and will continue to be a focus for the rest of Year 2 and into Year 3 and Work Package 21, as we align with the Drivers.

4.4. The Primary Training Package

While the work package contributed significant documentation for deployment and usage of **Five Safes TES** Tools, and developed the supporting **Analysis Types for TREs** training material, the last piece of work was to bring those developments together into a cohesive focused package aimed at TRE Operators, to allow them to achieve the learning goals outlined in the scope of the deliverable.

4.5. Related work

The work to prepare this deliverable, particularly in working with partners within and outside of EOSC-ENTRUST to deploy and explore the use of the **Five Safes TES** tools, resulted in work in the DARE UK TRevolution programme to define **Federated Research Patterns** and **Weaves**. That work intersects closely with Five Safes TES as a deployable demonstrator and helps communication around workflow processing and other approaches to federated research within TREs.

5. Conclusions

The deliverable provides required training materials to demonstrate federated workflow processing using the current version of the **Five Safes TES** tools, and serves as a training companion to the **Deployable Demonstrator, D20.1**, for TRE Operators. It provides the

information needed for TRE Operators to replicate the Deployable Demonstrator for themselves.

It introduces a way of looking at federated workflow processing not based solely on the capabilities of the tools, instead providing a resource in **Analysis Types for TREs** by which TRE Operators can explore how what patterns they find acceptable affect what analysis can be achieved. This resource is designed as an interactive illustration for its audiences. The audiences align directly with those identified in this training package, and the analysis types align directly to those detailed in the Federated Research Patterns documentation[26].

The material is framed specifically for its target audience, adding direction and clarity but only for the specific group catered for.

The deliverable relies on its source materials, notably the **Federated Research** documentation, including the **Five Safes TES** Tools documentation, and other documentation of supporting software such as Funnel, KeyCloak and MinIO.

6. Next steps

Much of this training package focuses on deployment and usage guidance for the Five Safes TES Tools, as well as high-level conceptual context for federated workflow processing. As work on communicating those concepts matures, and indeed development work on the tools themselves continues, training material and documentation will need to be expanded and refined.

Looking to year 3 of EOSC-ENTRUST, Work Package 21 will require material on Analysis Types and Patterns to align with Driver use cases.

Incorporating the RO-Crate component of the Work Package will require material on provenance requirements, and benefits of the Five Safes RO-Crate profile.

The limited target audience also limits the scope of this package. There is value in framing the material to cater to specific audiences, so perhaps in future additional tailored structures for other audiences could be considered.

As the deliverable was prepared within Work Package 20, we are keen to receive feedback across the project and beyond, which will inform where to target improvements and feed into work for the second training package, D21.2.

We will also seek to align with Work Package 14, given their training package outputs to date, to ensure consistency in terminology and explore colocating materials e.g. onto the same website.

7. Impact

This deliverable provides a focused view of material in order to target specific learning outcomes. While this results in a deliberately restricted scope for the material, it has already positively impacted audiences internally, by helping in the cross-institution deployment of the **Five Safes TES** Tools and running of federated analysis as part of the **Second Deployable Demonstrator, D20.1**. The developed material is also already being used for the same purpose with other parties interested in federated research using **Five Safes TES**.

With feedback gained from the publishing and therefore wider usage of these materials, future materials can be enhanced, and further materials developed with a wider scope and target audience, increasing the impact of future content. Feedback and response to this training package will also inform future development of the Five Safes Tools, supporting communication material, and approaches to federated research in general.

8. References

- [1] **First Training Package Website.** <https://entrust.federated-research.com>
- [2] **Deliverable D20.1: Second Deployable Demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows.** Google Docs (project internal).
https://docs.google.com/document/d/1A80GDugOTjWkpnbo_jHE5xdh_Pe39ko1
- [3] **First Training Package Website (Source Snapshot).**
<https://github.com/federated-research/entrust-training/tree/4a15656024ab7226d614dbcf7552c0c50c718f90>
- [4] **Analysis Types for TREs Website.**
<https://health-informatics-uon.github.io/analysis-types-for-TREs/>
- [5] **Federated Research Website.** <https://docs.federated-analytics.ac.uk>
- [6] **Five Safes TES Submission Deployment Requirements (Source Snapshot).**
<https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/submission/requirements.mdx>
- [7] **Five Safes TES Submission Deployment Guide (Source Snapshot).**
<https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/submission/deploy.mdx>
- [8] **Five Safes TES TRE Agent Deployment Requirements (Source Snapshot).**
https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/tre_agent/requirements.mdx

[9] **Five Safes TES TRE Components Deployment Guide (Source Snapshot).**

https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/tre_agent/deploy.mdx

[10] **Five Safes TES Funnel Deployment Guide (Source Snapshot).**

https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/five_safes_tes/tes/install_funnel.mdx

[11] **Five Safes TES Egress Configuration Guide (Source Snapshot).**

https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/tre_agent/guides/connecttoegress.mdx

[12] **Five Safes TES Project Setup Overview (Source Snapshot).**

https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/submission/guides/project_setup.mdx

[13] **Five Safes TES Complete Project Setup Process (Source Snapshot).**

<https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/submission/guides/submissionManagerAddingNewProject.mdx>

[14] **Five Safes TES Create a User Guide (Source Snapshot).**

<https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/submission/guides/keycloakAdminAddingNewUser.mdx>

[15] **Five Safes TES Complete Researcher Enrolment Guide (Source Snapshot).**

<https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/submission/guides/addresearchertoplatfrom.mdx>

[16] **Five Safes TES Add a Person to a Federation Guide (Source Snapshot).**

<https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/submission/guides/submissionManagerAddingNewPerson.mdx>

[17] **Five Safes TES Add a Person to a Project Guide (Source Snapshot).**

<https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/submission/guides/addresearchertoproject.mdx>

[18] **Five Safes TES Connect a TRE Agent Guide (Source Snapshot).**

<https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/submission/guides/addtreagent.mdx>

[19] **Five Safes TES TRE Project Approval Guide (Source Snapshot).**

https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/tre_agent/guides/TREManagerApprovingProject.mdx

[20] **Five Safes TES Submission API Token Guide (Source Snapshot).**

https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/submission/guides/get_token.mdx

[21] **Five Safes TES Hello World Submission Guide (Source Snapshot).**

<https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/submission/tasks/quickstart.mdx>

[22] **Five Safes TES Demonstration Analysis Submission Guide (Source Snapshot).**

https://github.com/federated-research/docs/blob/56921cef2ede65450f8ea7a11d63634a77761a8f/website/pages/submission/tasks/run_analysis.mdx

[23] **The statbarn: A New Model for Output Statistical Disclosure Control**

https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-69651-0_19

[24] **Computing extremely accurate quantiles Using t-digests**

<https://arxiv.org/abs/1902.04023>

[25] **Health Data Research UK and National Research Foundation Singapore formalise landmark partnership in health data science**

<https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/news/health-data-research-uk-and-national-research-foundation-singapore-formalise-landmark-partnership-in-health-data-science/>

[26] **Federated Research Patterns Analysis Types**

https://docs.federated-analytics.ac.uk/federated_research_patterns/patterns#analytical

[27] **Health Data Research UK** <https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/>

[28] **University of Swansea Medical School** <https://www.swansea.ac.uk/medicine/>

[29] **Machine learning models in trusted research environments - Understanding operational risks** <https://doi.org/10.23889/ijpds.v8i1.2165>